

An Ontology-Based Metamodel for the Analysis and Management of Social Debt in Software Development Teams

Repository Overview

This repository provides a collection of documents that offer a detailed overview of the process followed to develop the domain ontology on social debt. The repository contains documents related to specific phases of the ontology construction and validation process, as described below:

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- Document presenting the results of the ontology evaluation using the Ontology Pitfall Scanner! (OOPS!), highlighting potential pitfalls and quality aspects of the Social Debt Ontology.
- Social_Debt_Ontology.owl
Main ontology file in OWL format, containing the complete formal representation of the Social Debt Ontology (OntoSocialDebt), including classes, properties, and relationships.

- `Social_debt_ontology.rdf`
Ontology serialized in RDF/XML format, suitable for interoperability and integration with semantic web applications.
- `Social_debt_ontology.ttl`
Ontology version in Turtle (TTL) syntax, providing a concise and human-readable representation of the ontology's semantic structure.